

1 **Title:**
2 Regulatory Logic of the *Chlamydomonas* CO₂-Concentrating Mechanism: Coupling
3 Carbon Flux, Energy Supply, and Pyrenoid Architecture
4
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21 **Abstract**

22 The algal CO₂-concentrating mechanism (CCM) elevates CO₂ around Rubisco, the
23 CO₂-fixing enzyme, through the coordinated action of inorganic carbon (Ci) uptake
24 systems, carbonic anhydrases (CAs), and CO₂-retention mechanisms, thereby
25 maintaining photosynthetic efficiency under CO₂-limiting conditions. Although CCMs
26 occur across diverse aquatic photosynthetic organisms, the green alga *Chlamydomonas*
27 *reinhardtii* has become the principal model for dissecting the molecular regulation of
28 the eukaryotic algal CCM, and this review focuses on regulatory mechanisms
29 established in this organism. Recent studies have clarified energy-supply networks that
30 support the CCM, including cyclic and pseudo-cyclic electron transfer, chloroplast–
31 mitochondrial cooperation, and mitochondrial relocation toward the cell periphery
32 during CCM induction, as well as multilayered regulatory circuits that tune CCM
33 function across timescales. These circuits include CCM1/CIA5-dependent
34 transcriptional control, Ca²⁺-binding protein CAS-dependent chloroplast Ca²⁺ signaling,
35 protein relocation, KEY1-dependent post-translational control of pyrenoid
36 architecture, and active repression by the CCM1/CIA5-binding protein CBP1. However,
37 these advances are still often discussed separately, and an explicit systems-level
38 synthesis of carbon flux, energy supply, pyrenoid architecture, and regulation remains
39 limited. Here, we describe the *Chlamydomonas* CCM as a coupled system in which Ci
40 transport routes, CA deployment, CO₂-retention mechanisms, electron-transfer
41 pathways, and regulatory circuits are dynamically coordinated according to CO₂
42 availability. We also discuss how far these regulatory layers may extend beyond
43 *Chlamydomonas* within green algae, emphasizing the limited conservation of
44 CCM1/CIA5- and LCR1-type transcriptional regulators and the presence of CAS-linked
45 chloroplast Ca²⁺ signaling in both *Chlamydomonas* and land plants. Finally, we consider
46 how this regulatory perspective can inform future CCM engineering, arguing that crop-
47 oriented designs may ultimately need not only transferred pyrenoid components but also
48 regulatory strategies that dynamically tune CCM activity according to carbon and
49 energy status.

50 **Introduction**

51 The CO₂-concentrating mechanism (CCM) is an active CO₂-delivery system that
52 elevates CO₂ around Rubisco, the CO₂-fixing enzyme, to compensate for its slow
53 carboxylation rate and competition with O₂. In aquatic photosynthetic organisms, CCMs
54 are implemented by different molecular components, but many rely on a shared
55 functional logic that combines active inorganic carbon (Ci) accumulation, localized
56 conversion of HCO₃⁻ to CO₂ by carbonic anhydrases (CAs), and CO₂ retention or
57 recapture. These principles have been established over several decades through studies
58 of diverse algae and other photosynthetic microorganisms (Giordano et al., 2005; Raven
59 et al., 2014; Reinfelder, 2011).

60 Among green algae, the molecular regulation of the CCM has been
61 investigated most deeply in *Chlamydomonas reinhardtii*. This review therefore uses the
62 *Chlamydomonas* CCM as its primary framework and focuses on regulatory mechanisms
63 that have been experimentally defined in this organism. Unless explicitly stated
64 otherwise, mechanistic discussions of CCM regulation refer to *Chlamydomonas*.
65 Evidence from other green algae is discussed only where it helps evaluate whether
66 *Chlamydomonas*-derived regulatory principles may extend beyond this model.

67 The structure, assembly, and engineering potential of the *Chlamydomonas*
68 pyrenoid have been reviewed extensively elsewhere (Barrett et al., 2021; He et al.,
69 2023; Catherall et al., 2025). Therefore, rather than providing another detailed review of
70 pyrenoid architecture, we focus here on the regulatory logic that coordinates carbon
71 flux, energy supply, protein localization, Ca²⁺-linked signaling, post-translational
72 modification, and transcriptional induction or repression in response to CO₂ availability.

73 Within this *Chlamydomonas* framework, the CCM is not simply a collection of
74 Ci transport proteins and CAs. Its operation requires photosynthetic ATP under CO₂-
75 limiting conditions (Giordano et al., 2005; Raven et al., 2014) and meeting this energy
76 cost requires alternative electron-transfer pathways within the chloroplast as well as
77 chloroplast–mitochondrial cooperation. CCM components must also be coordinated
78 across timescales from seconds to hours in response to fluctuating environmental CO₂.
79 A full understanding of the CCM therefore requires a perspective that treats carbon flux,
80 energy supply, pyrenoid architecture, and regulation as interconnected parts of a
81 coupled system.

82 Recent advances in *Chlamydomonas* now allow such an integrated view. On
83 the energy side, Burlacot et al. (2022) demonstrated that cyclic and pseudo-cyclic
84 electron transfer are essential for driving the CCM, and Findinier et al. (2024) showed
85 that mitochondria relocate to the cell periphery during CCM induction, consistent with

86 respiratory support for CCM performance. On the regulatory side, CCM1/CIA5 controls
87 the induction of many CCM genes under CO₂-limiting conditions (Fang et al., 2012;
88 Fukuzawa et al., 2001; Miura et al., 2004; Xiang et al., 2001). This transcriptional
89 framework has been expanded by studies of LCIB–LCIC relocalization (Toyokawa et
90 al., 2020; Yamano et al., 2010; Yamano et al., 2022), CAS-dependent Ca²⁺-linked
91 feedback (Shimamura et al., 2023; Wang et al., 2016), *in vitro* biochemical evidence for
92 CCM1/CIA5 DNA binding (Chen and Spalding, 2026), active repression by the nuclear
93 protein CBP1 (Shimamura et al., 2026), condensate-level control by the pyrenoid kinase
94 KEY1 (He et al., 2026), and the joint operation of CCM induction and photorespiration
95 during acclimation to CO₂-limiting conditions (Dao et al., 2025). Together, these studies
96 show that the *Chlamydomonas* CCM is an environmentally responsive system in which
97 transport, energy supply, pyrenoid architecture, transcriptional regulation, and post-
98 translational control are tightly coupled.

99 In this review, we use the *Chlamydomonas* CCM as the primary framework for
100 integrating driving mechanism, energy supply, and multilayered regulation. We first
101 outline how Ci transport routes, CA deployment, pyrenoid architecture, and CO₂-
102 retention mechanisms are rewired according to CO₂ availability. We then discuss how
103 electron-transfer pathways and chloroplast–mitochondrial cooperation meet the
104 energetic demands of Ci transport and localized CO₂ generation. Finally, we examine
105 how transcriptional control, protein relocalization, Ca²⁺-linked feedback, condensate-
106 level post-translational regulation, and transcriptional repression coordinate these
107 components. We close by considering how the *Chlamydomonas* regulatory architecture
108 may or may not extend to other green algae, and what this means for future engineering
109 applications. Figure 1 summarizes this framework: Fig. 1A integrates Ci transport,
110 energy supply, and regulatory modules, whereas Fig. 1B illustrates how regulatory state
111 and selected chloroplast protein localizations change across HC, LC, and VLC
112 conditions.

113

114 **Operational Definitions of HC, LC, and VLC in *Chlamydomonas***

115 Throughout this review, we use the terms high CO₂ (HC), low CO₂ (LC), and very-low
116 CO₂ (VLC) as operational acclimation states rather than as universally fixed gas-phase
117 values. In controlled gas-phase experiments, these states are often separated clearly by
118 the supplied CO₂ concentration. For example, cells grown on plates or in chambers may
119 be exposed to HC conditions such as 5% CO₂, LC conditions approximating air-level
120 CO₂ around 0.04%, or VLC conditions such as 0.01% CO₂. Such gas-phase definitions

121 are particularly useful for growth assays because the imposed atmospheric CO₂
122 concentration is well controlled and reproducible (Toyokawa et al., 2020).

123 In liquid culture, however, the distinction between LC and VLC is more
124 difficult to define from the supplied gas phase alone. Dissolved CO₂ depends not only
125 on the aerated CO₂ concentration but also on pH, total dissolved inorganic carbon, gas
126 exchange, buffering capacity, cell density, and carbonic anhydrase activity. Therefore, a
127 nominal gas-phase CO₂ concentration does not always correspond directly to the CO₂
128 concentration experienced by the cell. For this reason, when discussing liquid-culture
129 experiments, we distinguish LC and VLC primarily by the calculated or measured
130 dissolved CO₂ concentration and by physiological markers of the acclimation state.

131 A useful operational boundary was provided by LCIB localization. LCIB is
132 dispersed in the chloroplast stroma under HC and LC conditions but relocates to the
133 pyrenoid periphery under VLC conditions. This reversible localization switch is
134 controlled by CO₂ concentration, with approximately 7 μM dissolved CO₂ as the
135 boundary between LC and VLC. In that framework, VLC corresponds to <7 μM
136 dissolved CO₂, LC to approximately 7–70 μM dissolved CO₂, and HC to >70 μM
137 dissolved CO₂ in liquid-culture assays (Yamano et al., 2022). This threshold also
138 matches physiological behavior of LCIB-related mutants and oxygen-evolution
139 responses, supporting the view that LC and VLC are distinct acclimation states rather
140 than simply different degrees of a single CO₂-limiting state (Wang and Spalding, 2014;
141 Yamano et al., 2022).

142 Accordingly, in this review, “CO₂-limiting conditions” is used as a broad term
143 that includes both LC and VLC. “LC” refers to moderate CO₂ limitation, including air-
144 level CO₂ conditions, in which the LCII–CAH1 route contributes substantially to CO₂
145 uptake and LCIB–LCIC remains largely stromal. LCIB-dependent recapture may still
146 contribute to C_i affinity, but pyrenoid-peripheral enrichment of LCIB–LCIC is a
147 hallmark of VLC rather than LC. “VLC” refers to more severe CO₂ limitation, typically
148 below the ~7 μM dissolved CO₂ boundary in liquid culture, in which LCIB–LCIC
149 relocalizes to the pyrenoid periphery and HCO₃⁻ uptake through the HLA3–LCIA–
150 BST–CAH3 axis becomes especially important. We use “HC” for high-CO₂-supplied
151 conditions in which the CCM is repressed or only weakly active. When possible, we
152 specify whether a statement refers to gas-phase CO₂, calculated dissolved CO₂, or a
153 biological marker such as LCIB localization.

154

155 **Driving Mechanism of the CCM**

156 In *Chlamydomonas*, efficient CCM operation can be described as the coordination of C_i
157 uptake, localized CO_2 generation, and CO_2 retention or recapture, each of which is
158 adjusted according to external CO_2 availability. First, C_i is accumulated through energy-
159 dependent uptake steps, including ABC-type HCO_3^- uptake at the plasma membrane
160 and subsequent transfer across the chloroplast envelope and thylakoid membrane.
161 Second, localized CA activity converts accumulated HCO_3^- to CO_2 in the immediate
162 vicinity of Rubisco. Third, diffusion barriers and recapture systems retain or recover
163 that CO_2 long enough for fixation.

164 Under VLC conditions, *Chlamydomonas* induces the plasma-membrane ABC-type
165 transporter HLA3, which contributes to HCO_3^- uptake (Duanmu et al., 2009; Gao et al.,
166 2015). HCO_3^- then crosses the chloroplast envelope through LCIA, a chloroplast-
167 envelope bicarbonate channel/transporter (Förster et al., 2023; Guo et al., 2026;
168 Yamano et al., 2015), and is thought to enter the thylakoid lumen through bestrophin-
169 like proteins BST1–3 (Mukherjee et al., 2019). In the pyrenoid-traversing thylakoid
170 tubules, the α -type CA CAH3 dehydrates HCO_3^- to CO_2 near the Rubisco-rich matrix
171 (Karlsson et al., 1998; Mackinder et al., 2017). A complementary recapture system is
172 provided by the stromal β -CA-like LCIB–LCIC complex. LCIB relocates to the
173 pyrenoid periphery under VLC conditions, where it is proposed to convert CO_2 leaking
174 from the fixation site back to HCO_3^- and help maintain the stromal C_i pool (Kasili et al.,
175 2023; Yamano et al., 2010; Yamano et al., 2022). Correct pyrenoid-peripheral
176 localization of LCIB depends on the starch sheath and LCIC (Toyokawa et al., 2020;
177 Yamano et al., 2022).

178 Under LC conditions, when CO_2 availability rises above the VLC range but
179 remains limiting, C_i acquisition can pivot toward a CO_2 -uptake route involving the
180 plasma-membrane protein LCI1 and the periplasmic CA CAH1. LCI1 functions in
181 active CO_2 uptake and is proposed to act as a plasma-membrane CO_2 channel (Kono et
182 al., 2020; Kono and Spalding, 2020), whereas CAH1 converts extracellular HCO_3^- to
183 CO_2 and thereby supports high C_i affinity, particularly under alkaline conditions
184 (Shimamura et al., 2024).

185 The efficiency of these uptake routes depends on pyrenoid architecture. CAH3-
186 and BST-enriched thylakoid tubules traverse the pyrenoid matrix, positioning luminal
187 HCO_3^- dehydration close to Rubisco (Mackinder et al., 2017; Mukherjee et al., 2019;
188 Hennacy et al., 2024). The starch sheath contributes to CCM performance by supporting
189 LCIB localization and is predicted to reduce CO_2 leakage from the Rubisco-rich matrix
190 (Fei et al., 2022; Toyokawa et al., 2020). The SAGA1–MITH1 module generates

191 matrix-traversing membranes, physically coupling lumenal C_i processing to the
192 pyrenoid matrix (Hennacy et al., 2024).

193 Taken together, the *Chlamydomonas* CCM is best viewed as a spatially organized
194 carbon-flux system. Its performance depends not on any single transporter, CA, or
195 structural element, but on the coordination of C_i uptake, localized CO_2 generation,
196 leakage recapture, diffusion limitation, and pyrenoid architecture.

197

198 **Energy Supply and Metabolic Integration in the CCM**

199 In *Chlamydomonas*, operation of the CCM imposes an additional energetic demand
200 under CO_2 -limiting conditions because C_i uptake, thylakoid lumen acidification, and
201 localized CO_2 generation all depend on photosynthetic energy supply. Meeting this
202 demand while maintaining Calvin–Benson cycle activity requires alternative electron-
203 transfer pathways that adjust the ATP/NADPH balance and sustain the proton motive
204 force (Burlacot et al., 2022; Giordano et al., 2005; Raven et al., 2014).

205 Within the chloroplast, PGRL1-dependent cyclic electron flow around
206 photosystem I and flavodiiron-protein-dependent pseudo-cyclic electron flow increase
207 the proton motive force without producing additional NADPH. Burlacot et al. (2022)
208 showed that these pathways are required to generate a low thylakoid lumen pH that is
209 essential for CCM function. The resulting ΔpH supports ATP synthesis and creates a
210 lumenal environment favorable for HCO_3^- dehydration by CAH3. This interpretation is
211 consistent with the thylakoid localization and CCM requirement of BST1–3 and CAH3,
212 and with biochemical evidence that CAH3 is most active at the slightly acidic pH values
213 expected in the illuminated thylakoid lumen (Benlloch et al., 2015; Karlsson et al.,
214 1998; Mukherjee et al., 2019).

215 Energy supply must also be considered together with pyrenoid architecture.
216 Modeling of the pyrenoid-based CCM indicates that efficient CO_2 concentration
217 requires localized CO_2 generation, correct enzyme placement, and a physical barrier that
218 limits CO_2 leakage from the pyrenoid matrix (Fei et al., 2022). Thus, the energetic role
219 of lumen acidification is inseparable from the spatial organization of CAH3, thylakoid
220 tubules, and Rubisco within the pyrenoid. Recent reviews have emphasized the same
221 principle as a key constraint for transferring pyrenoid-based CCMs into plants
222 (Catherall et al., 2025).

223 Chloroplast-to-mitochondrion electron flow provides another route for
224 balancing reductant and ATP demand. Burlacot et al. (2022) proposed that this pathway
225 contributes to energizing non-thylakoid C_i uptake steps, probably by supporting
226 respiratory ATP production. Consistent with this view, mitochondria relocate from a

227 more central distribution toward the cell periphery during CCM induction, supporting a
228 functional connection between respiration and CCM performance (Findinier et al.,
229 2024). More recent quantitative work further showed that cyclic, pseudo-cyclic, and
230 chloroplast-to-mitochondrion electron flows can compensate for one another, and that at
231 least one of these alternative pathways is required to sustain efficient CO₂ fixation
232 (Peltier et al., 2024).

233 Integration with central carbon metabolism is more nuanced than a simple
234 photorespiration-suppression model. During CO₂-limiting acclimation, CCM and
235 photorespiratory genes are simultaneously induced, and both programs are linked to
236 CCM1/CIA5-dependent regulation. Physiological analyses further show that
237 photorespiration remains active when the CCM is operational, indicating that CCM
238 induction reduces but does not eliminate oxygenation pressure around Rubisco (Dao et
239 al., 2025). Inefficient CO₂ retention would also increase the demand for Ci recapture
240 and re-entry into the concentrating cycle, thereby increasing the energetic burden of the
241 CCM as a whole.

242 Taken together, energy supply in the *Chlamydomonas* CCM is distributed
243 across multiple pathways rather than assigned to a single ATP source. It is a flexible
244 network that couples thylakoid ΔpH, alternative electron flow, chloroplast–
245 mitochondrial cooperation, pyrenoid architecture, and central carbon metabolism. This
246 energetic network provides the foundation on which the regulatory circuits discussed
247 below can tune CCM activity according to CO₂ availability and cellular metabolic state.
248

249 **Multilayered Regulation of the CCM**

250 In *Chlamydomonas*, CCM activity is coordinated by regulatory layers that act over
251 different timescales, from rapid changes in protein localization and post-translational
252 state to slower transcriptional induction and repression.

253 A central transcriptional layer is controlled by CCM1/CIA5, a Zn-finger-
254 containing regulator required for the induction of many CCM genes under CO₂-limiting
255 conditions. These include genes encoding Ci transport proteins and CAs such as *HLA3*,
256 *LCIA*, *LCIB*, *LCIC*, *CAH1*, and *CAH3* (Fang et al., 2012; Fukuzawa et al., 2001; Miura
257 et al., 2004; Xiang et al., 2001; Yamano et al., 2008). Earlier studies did not detect
258 direct DNA binding by CCM1/CIA5, but recent *in vitro* work using purified full-length
259 CIA5 demonstrated specific binding to a GC-rich motif found in promoters of CIA5-
260 dependent genes (Chen and Spalding, 2026). This provides the first *in vitro* biochemical
261 evidence that CCM1/CIA5 can directly recognize promoter DNA. Recent work further
262 indicates that CCM1/CIA5 coordinates part of the photorespiratory response to CO₂

263 limitation, suggesting that it governs a broader carbon-acclimation state rather than only
264 a canonical CCM regulon (Dao et al., 2025). The primary CO₂/HCO₃⁻ sensor upstream
265 of CCM1/CIA5 remains unknown.

266 Downstream of CCM1/CIA5, branch-specific transcriptional regulators further
267 partition the response to CO₂ limitation. The Myb-type transcription factor LCR1
268 regulates *CAH1* and other target genes in response to CO₂ limitation, indicating that
269 CCM1/CIA5-dependent induction is subdivided into more specific transcriptional
270 modules (Yoshioka et al., 2004). The physiological importance of CAH1 in Ci
271 acquisition has recently been reinforced by genetic analysis (Shimamura et al., 2024).

272 A second layer involves spatial reorganization of CCM components. LCIB–
273 LCIC localization provides a useful marker for distinguishing LC and VLC states. LCIB
274 remains largely dispersed in the chloroplast stroma under HC and LC conditions but
275 relocates to the pyrenoid periphery under VLC conditions. This relocation is
276 proposed to promote recapture of CO₂ leaking from the fixation site and depends on the
277 starch sheath (Toyokawa et al., 2020; Yamano et al., 2010; Yamano et al., 2022). This
278 CO₂-dependent change in LCIB–LCIC localization is included in the HC/LC/VLC
279 switch shown in Fig. 1B. In parallel, BST1–3 and CAH3 are positioned within
280 pyrenoid-traversing thylakoid tubules, placing HCO₃⁻ transport and luminal CO₂
281 generation near the Rubisco-rich matrix (Mackinder et al., 2017; Mukherjee et al.,
282 2019). At the level of pyrenoid architecture, SAGA1 and MITH1 generate the matrix-
283 traversing membranes themselves. Mutants lacking either factor lose these membranes
284 and show growth defects under CO₂-limiting conditions (Hennacy et al., 2024).

285 A third regulatory layer is provided by CAS-dependent Ca²⁺-linked signaling.
286 CAS is a chloroplast Ca²⁺-binding protein that changes localization in response to CO₂
287 conditions and regulates nuclear CCM gene expression through a chloroplast-to-nucleus
288 signal (Wang et al., 2016). SAGA1 also links pyrenoid architecture to CAS-dependent
289 signaling. Disruption of SAGA1 impairs CAS localization to the pyrenoid and weakens
290 CAS-dependent expression of nuclear genes encoding Ci transporters, indicating that
291 pyrenoid structure itself participates in CCM regulation (Shimamura et al., 2023). The
292 simplified CAS localization pattern shown in Fig. 1B highlights this regulatory
293 connection between pyrenoid-associated chloroplast signaling and nuclear CCM gene
294 expression.

295 Post-translational regulation provides another layer of control. Early
296 phosphoproteomic work showed that CO₂ limitation alters phosphorylation of multiple
297 CCM-associated proteins (Turkina et al., 2006). A functional precedent is CAH3
298 phosphorylation. Acclimation to CO₂ limitation promotes CAH3 phosphorylation,

299 partial activation, and redistribution within thylakoid membranes, indicating that
300 phosphorylation can tune both enzymatic activity and spatial organization of CCM
301 components (Blanco-Rivero et al., 2012). More recently, the pyrenoid-localized kinase
302 KEY1 was shown to phosphorylate EPYC1 at Rubisco-binding sites. This weakens
303 Rubisco–EPYC1 interactions and controls pyrenoid size, number, and dissolution (He et
304 al., 2026). Notably, KEY1 is induced by CO₂-limiting stress in a CCM1/CIA5-
305 dependent manner, indicating that transcriptional induction can feed directly into
306 condensate-level control of pyrenoid architecture (Shimamura et al., 2026). A key
307 unresolved question is whether CO₂-limiting acclimation also induces phosphatase
308 activities that reset EPYC1 phosphorylation and restore pyrenoid condensability.

309 In addition to these inductive regulatory layers, the CCM is actively repressed
310 under HC conditions. The nuclear protein CBP1 interacts with CCM1/CIA5 and
311 represses the expression of 27 of 41 CCM1-dependent genes under HC conditions. In
312 *cbp1* mutants, CAH1 and LCIB protein levels increase and Ci affinity rises even under
313 HC conditions. These findings indicate that CBP1 prevents unnecessary CCM
314 activation when CO₂ is abundant, thereby contributing to energy conservation
315 (Shimamura et al., 2026). The CobW/CobW_C GTP-binding metallochaperone module
316 in CBP1 raises the possibility that metal-dependent regulation contributes to CCM
317 repression. This HC repression state, together with the release of CCM1/CIA5-
318 dependent induction under CO₂-limiting conditions, is schematized in Fig. 1B.

319 How far this regulatory architecture extends to other green algae remains an
320 important open question. The *Chlamydomonas* transcriptional regulator CCM1/CIA5
321 appears to be a lineage-restricted component rather than a broadly conserved green-
322 plant regulator. A CCM1/CIA5 ortholog has been reported in *Volvox carteri*, where
323 cells grown under CO₂-limiting conditions show increased Ci affinity and the *Volvox*
324 protein shares 51% amino-acid identity with *Chlamydomonas* CCM1/CIA5, including
325 conservation of key N-terminal and zinc-finger-related regions (Yamano et al., 2011;
326 Brueggeman et al., 2012). Genomic analyses have also annotated CIA5/CCM1 among
327 *Chlamydomonas* CCM-associated orthologs in the trebouxiophyte *Coccomyxa*
328 *subellipsoidea* C-169, although functional conservation of this regulator has not been
329 demonstrated (Blanc et al., 2012). Thus, CCM1/CIA5-dependent transcriptional control
330 may represent a specialized regulatory solution in a subset of chlorophytes.

331 The conservation of LCR1-type branch-specific regulation is also uncertain.
332 LCR1 is a divergent 1R-Myb transcription factor in *Chlamydomonas*, and orthology
333 outside closely related green algae should be inferred cautiously without dedicated
334 Myb-family phylogenetic analysis (Yoshioka et al., 2004; Brueggeman et al., 2012).

335 By contrast, CAS is a more broadly conserved chloroplast Ca²⁺ signaling
336 component. CAS functions in *Chlamydomonas* CCM regulation and photoacclimation,
337 whereas *Arabidopsis* CAS is required for Ca²⁺-dependent stomatal regulation and
338 chloroplast-mediated signaling (Nomura et al., 2008; Petroustos et al., 2011; Wang et
339 al., 2016; Weinl et al., 2008). The *Chlamydomonas* CCM therefore appears to combine
340 lineage-restricted transcriptional regulation with chloroplast Ca²⁺ signaling modules that
341 have functional counterparts in both *Chlamydomonas* and land plants.

342

343 **Conclusions and Future Perspectives**

344 Taken together, recent work supports a view of the *Chlamydomonas* CCM as a coupled
345 system in which Ci transport, energy supply, pyrenoid architecture, and regulation are
346 inseparable. Flexible Ci uptake routes, lumen acidification, chloroplast–mitochondrial
347 cooperation, CO₂ retention, and multilayered control circuits together determine
348 whether Rubisco remains supplied with high local CO₂ under fluctuating environments.
349 At the same time, conservation of individual regulatory modules is uneven across green
350 algae. CCM1/CIA5-dependent transcriptional regulation, and possibly LCR1-type
351 branch-specific control, appear relatively restricted, whereas CAS-linked chloroplast
352 Ca²⁺ signaling has functional counterparts in both *Chlamydomonas* and land plants.

353 The next challenge is to identify how the system switches between carbon-
354 replete HC conditions and CO₂-limiting LC/VLC states. The upstream CO₂/HCO₃⁻
355 sensor for CCM1/CIA5 remains unknown, and one plausible possibility is that sensing
356 is mediated by a multi-component signaling module rather than by a single receptor. As
357 a conceptual analogy, *Arabidopsis* guard cells show that CO₂/HCO₃⁻ sensing can be
358 distributed across interacting proteins. The HT1–MPK4/12 module functions as a
359 primary CO₂/HCO₃⁻ sensor, and CA4 can regulate the SLAC1 anion channel through a
360 binding function that is separable from CA catalytic activity (Takahashi et al., 2022; Xia
361 et al., 2026). These findings raise the possibility that *Chlamydomonas* CO₂ sensing may
362 also involve modular interactions among CAs, kinases, and membrane transport
363 proteins, although no equivalent upstream sensor has yet been identified in
364 *Chlamydomonas*.

365 KEY1 now provides a mechanistic entry point into condensate-level CCM
366 regulation. Because KEY1 is induced by CO₂-limiting stress in a CCM1/CIA5-
367 dependent manner (Shimamura et al., 2026), transcriptional induction provides a route
368 into pyrenoid phase control. Mechanistically, KEY1 phosphorylates EPYC1 at Rubisco-
369 binding sites, weakens Rubisco–EPYC1 interactions, and regulates pyrenoid size,
370 number, and dissolution (He et al., 2026). This raises the reciprocal question of whether

371 CO₂-limiting acclimation also induces phosphatase activities that reset EPYC1
372 phosphorylation and restore pyrenoid condensability. No phosphatase has yet been
373 shown to dephosphorylate EPYC1 or to promote pyrenoid condensation. Nevertheless,
374 identifying phosphatase activities induced under CO₂-limiting conditions is now a
375 testable way to examine whether pyrenoid assembly is regulated by reversible
376 phosphorylation. Time-resolved phosphoproteomics, acute kinase and phosphatase
377 perturbations, and *in vitro* reconstitution of Rubisco–EPYC1–KEY1 reactions with
378 candidate phosphatases could reveal whether pyrenoid assembly is actively tuned by
379 reversible phosphorylation cycles.

380 The distinction between transferring CCM components and recreating their
381 regulatory logic is important for engineering. Current efforts to build pyrenoid-based
382 CCMs in plants have focused mainly on transferring or reconstituting structural and
383 catalytic components, such as Rubisco condensation, pyrenoid matrix formation, CO₂-
384 retention structures, transport steps, and CAs (Atkinson et al., 2020; Fei et al., 2022;
385 Catherall et al., 2025). These approaches establish the feasibility of component transfer,
386 but they do not yet recreate the regulatory logic by which the *Chlamydomonas* CCM is
387 switched on, restrained, spatially reorganized, and energetically coordinated according
388 to CO₂ availability. Thus, a “switchable CCM” should be viewed at present as a design
389 principle emerging from *Chlamydomonas* regulation rather than as an already
390 demonstrated crop-engineering module. Future designs may need to combine pyrenoid
391 components with plant-compatible regulatory systems, such as inducible promoters,
392 carbon- or energy-responsive sensors, and reversible phosphorylation switches, so that
393 CCM activity can track carbon status, light-dependent energy supply, and
394 developmental context. For heterologous photosynthetic systems, the ability to switch
395 CCM activity in response to carbon and energy status may be as critical as the choice of
396 individual transporters, CAs, or pyrenoid structural components.

397

398 **Conflict of Interest**

399 The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial
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407 **References**

- 408 Atkinson, N., Mao, Y., Chan, K. X., and McCormick, A. J. (2020). Condensation of
409 Rubisco into a proto-pyrenoid in higher plant chloroplasts. *Nat. Commun.* 11:6303.
410 doi: 10.1038/s41467-020-20132-0
411
- 412 Barrett, J., Girr, P., and Mackinder, L. C. M. (2021). Pyrenoids: CO₂-fixing phase
413 separated liquid organelles. *Biochim. Biophys. Acta Mol. Cell Res.* 1868:118949.
414 doi: 10.1016/j.bbamcr.2021.118949
415
- 416 Benlloch, R., Shevela, D., Hainzl, T., Grundström, C., Shutova, T., Messinger, J., et al.
417 (2015). Crystal structure and functional characterization of photosystem II-associated
418 carbonic anhydrase CAH3 in *Chlamydomonas reinhardtii*. *Plant Physiol.* 167, 950–
419 962. doi: 10.1104/pp.114.253591
420
- 421 Blanc, G., Agarkova, I., Grimwood, J., Kuo, A., Brueggeman, A., Dunigan, D. D., et al.
422 (2012). The genome of the polar eukaryotic microalga *Coccomyxa subellipsoidea*
423 reveals traits of cold adaptation. *Genome Biol.* 13:R39. doi: 10.1186/gb-2012-13-5-
424 r39
425
- 426 Blanco-Rivero, A., Shutova, T., Román, M. J., Villarejo, A., and Martinez, F. (2012).
427 Phosphorylation controls the localization and activation of the luminal carbonic
428 anhydrase in *Chlamydomonas reinhardtii*. *PLoS One* 7:e49063. doi:
429 10.1371/journal.pone.0049063
430
- 431 Brueggeman, A. J., Gangadharaiah, D. S., Cserhati, M. F., Casero, D., Weeks, D. P., and
432 Ladunga, I. (2012). Activation of the carbon concentrating mechanism by CO₂
433 deprivation coincides with massive transcriptional restructuring in *Chlamydomonas*
434 *reinhardtii*. *Plant Cell* 24, 1860–1875. doi: 10.1105/tpc.111.093435
435
- 436 Burlacot, A., Dao, O., Auroy, P., Cuiné, S., Li-Beisson, Y., and Peltier, G. (2022).
437 Alternative photosynthesis pathways drive the algal CO₂-concentrating mechanism.
438 *Nature* 605, 366–371. doi: 10.1038/s41586-022-04662-9
439
- 440 Catherall, E., Musial, S., Atkinson, N., Walker, C. E., Mackinder, L. C. M., and
441 McCormick, A. J. (2025). From algae to plants: understanding pyrenoid-based CO₂-
442 concentrating mechanisms. *Trends Biochem. Sci.* 50, 33–45. doi:

443 10.1016/j.tibs.2024.10.010
444
445 Chen, B., and Spalding, M. H. (2026). Investigation of the DNA binding ability of CIA5
446 in *Chlamydomonas reinhardtii*. *Plant Mol. Biol. Rep.* 44:42. doi: 10.1007/s11105-
447 025-01670-7
448
449 Dao, O., Bertrand, M., Alseekh, S., Veillet, F., Auroy, P., Nguyen, P.-C., et al. (2025).
450 The green algae CO₂ concentrating mechanism and photorespiration jointly operate
451 during acclimation to low CO₂. *Nat. Commun.* 16:5296. doi: 10.1038/s41467-025-
452 60525-7
453
454 Duanmu, D., Miller, A. R., Horken, K. M., Weeks, D. P., and Spalding, M. H. (2009).
455 Knockdown of limiting-CO₂-induced gene HLA3 decreases HCO₃⁻ transport and
456 photosynthetic Ci affinity in *Chlamydomonas reinhardtii*. *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci.*
457 U.S.A. 106, 5990–5995. doi: 10.1073/pnas.0812885106
458
459 Fang, W., Si, Y., Douglass, S., Casero, D., Merchant, S. S., Pellegrini, M., et al. (2012).
460 Transcriptome-wide changes in *Chlamydomonas reinhardtii* gene expression
461 regulated by carbon dioxide and the CO₂-concentrating mechanism regulator
462 CIA5/CCM1. *Plant Cell* 24, 1876–1893. doi: 10.1105/tpc.112.097949
463
464 Fei, C., Wilson, A. T., Mangan, N. M., Wingreen, N. S., and Jonikas, M. C. (2022).
465 Modelling the pyrenoid-based CO₂-concentrating mechanism provides insights into
466 its operating principles and a roadmap for its engineering into crops. *Nat. Plants* 8,
467 583–595. doi: 10.1038/s41477-022-01153-7
468
469 Findinier, J., Joubert, L.-M., Fakhimi, N., Schmid, M. F., Malkovskiy, A. V., Chiu, W.,
470 et al. (2024). Dramatic changes in mitochondrial subcellular location and morphology
471 accompany activation of the CO₂ concentrating mechanism. *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci.*
472 U.S.A. 121:e2407548121. doi: 10.1073/pnas.2407548121
473
474 Förster, B., Rourke, L. M., Weerasooriya, H. N., Pabuayon, I. C. M., Rolland, V., Au, E.
475 K., et al. (2023). The *Chlamydomonas reinhardtii* chloroplast envelope protein LCIA
476 transports bicarbonate in planta. *J. Exp. Bot.* 74, 3651–3666. doi:
477 10.1093/jxb/erad116
478

479 Fukuzawa, H., Miura, K., Ishizaki, K., Kucho, K., Saito, T., Kohinata, T., et al. (2001).
480 Ccm1, a regulatory gene controlling the induction of a carbon-concentrating
481 mechanism in *Chlamydomonas reinhardtii* by sensing CO₂ availability. *Proc. Natl.*
482 *Acad. Sci. U.S.A.* 98, 5347–5352. doi: 10.1073/pnas.081593498
483
484 Gao, H., Wang, Y., Fei, X., Wright, D. A., and Spalding, M. H. (2015). Expression
485 activation and functional analysis of HLA3, a putative inorganic carbon transporter in
486 *Chlamydomonas reinhardtii*. *Plant J.* 82, 1–11. doi: 10.1111/tpj.12788
487
488 Giordano, M., Beardall, J., and Raven, J. A. (2005). CO₂ concentrating mechanisms in
489 algae: mechanisms, environmental modulation, and evolution. *Annu. Rev. Plant Biol.*
490 56, 99–131. doi: 10.1146/annurev.arplant.56.032604.144052
491
492 Guo, J., Yang, Z., Zhang, X., Liu, F., Ma, M., Yu, F., et al. (2026). Structure of
493 *Chlamydomonas reinhardtii* LciA guided the engineering of FNT family proteins to
494 gain bicarbonate transport activity. *Nat. Plants* 12, 231–240. doi: 10.1038/s41477-
495 025-02200-9
496
497 He, S., Crans, V. L., and Jonikas, M. C. (2023). The pyrenoid: the eukaryotic CO₂-
498 concentrating organelle. *Plant Cell* 35, 3236–3259. doi: 10.1093/plcell/koad157
499
500 He, S., Lemma, L. M., Martinez-Calvo, A., He, G., Hennacy, J. H., Wang, L., et al.
501 (2026). Kinase KEY1 controls pyrenoid condensate size throughout the cell cycle by
502 disrupting phase separation interactions. *Nat. Cell Biol.* 28, 725–738. doi:
503 10.1038/s41556-026-01908-w
504
505 Hennacy, J. H., Atkinson, N., Kayser-Browne, A., Ergun, S. L., Franklin, E., Wang, L.,
506 et al. (2024). SAGA1 and MITH1 produce matrix-traversing membranes in the CO₂-
507 fixing pyrenoid. *Nat. Plants* 10, 2038–2051. doi: 10.1038/s41477-024-01847-0
508
509 Karlsson, J., Clarke, A. K., Chen, Z. Y., Huggins, S. Y., Park, Y. I., Husic, H. D., et al.
510 (1998). A novel alpha-type carbonic anhydrase associated with the thylakoid
511 membrane in *Chlamydomonas reinhardtii* is required for growth at ambient CO₂.
512 *EMBO J.* 17, 1208–1216. doi: 10.1093/emboj/17.5.1208
513
514 Kasili, R. W., Rai, A. K., and Moroney, J. V. (2023). LCIB functions as a carbonic

515 anhydrase: evidence from yeast and Arabidopsis carbonic anhydrase knockout
516 mutants. *Photosynth. Res.* 156, 193–204. doi: 10.1007/s11120-023-01005-1
517

518 Kono, A., and Spalding, M. H. (2020). LCI1, a *Chlamydomonas reinhardtii* plasma
519 membrane protein, functions in active CO₂ uptake under low CO₂. *Plant J.* 102,
520 1127–1141. doi: 10.1111/tpj.14761
521

522 Kono, A., Chou, T.-H., Radhakrishnan, A., Bolla, J. R., Sankar, K., Shome, S., et al.
523 (2020). Structure and function of LCI1: a plasma membrane CO₂ channel in the
524 *Chlamydomonas* CO₂ concentrating mechanism. *Plant J.* 102, 1107–1126. doi:
525 10.1111/tpj.14745
526

527 Mackinder, L. C. M., Chen, C., Leib, R. D., Patena, W., Blum, S. R., Rodman, M., et al.
528 (2017). A spatial interactome reveals the protein organization of the algal CO₂-
529 concentrating mechanism. *Cell* 171, 133–147.e14. doi: 10.1016/j.cell.2017.08.044
530

531 Miura, K., Yamano, T., Yoshioka, S., Kohinata, T., Inoue, Y., Taniguchi, F., et al. (2004).
532 Expression profiling-based identification of CO₂-responsive genes regulated by
533 CCM1 controlling a carbon-concentrating mechanism in *Chlamydomonas reinhardtii*.
534 *Plant Physiol.* 135, 1595–1607. doi: 10.1104/pp.104.041400
535

536 Mukherjee, A., Lau, C. S., Walker, C. E., Rai, A. K., Prejean, C. I., Yates, G., et al.
537 (2019). Thylakoid localized bestrophin-like proteins are essential for the CO₂
538 concentrating mechanism of *Chlamydomonas reinhardtii*. *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci.*
539 U.S.A. 116, 16915–16920. doi: 10.1073/pnas.1909706116
540

541 Nomura, H., Komori, T., Kobori, M., Nakahira, Y., and Shiina, T. (2008). Evidence for
542 chloroplast control of external Ca²⁺-induced cytosolic Ca²⁺ transients and stomatal
543 closure. *Plant J.* 53, 988–998. doi: 10.1111/j.1365-313X.2007.03390.x
544

545 Peltier, G., Stoffel, C., Findinier, J., Madireddi, S. K., Dao, O., Epting, V., et al. (2024).
546 Alternative electron pathways of photosynthesis power green algal CO₂ capture.
547 *Plant Cell* 36, 4132–4142. doi: 10.1093/plcell/koae143
548

549 Petroustos, D., Busch, A., Janßen, I., Trompelt, K., Bergner, S. V., Weinl, S., et al.
550 (2011). The chloroplast calcium sensor CAS is required for photoacclimation in

551 *Chlamydomonas reinhardtii*. *Plant Cell* 23, 2950–2963. doi: 10.1105/tpc.111.087973
552
553 Raven, J. A., Beardall, J., and Giordano, M. (2014). Energy costs of carbon dioxide
554 concentrating mechanisms in aquatic organisms. *Photosynth. Res.* 121, 111–124. doi:
555 10.1007/s11120-013-9962-7
556
557 Reinfelder, J. R. (2011). Carbon concentrating mechanisms in eukaryotic marine
558 phytoplankton. *Annu. Rev. Mar. Sci.* 3, 291–315. doi: 10.1146/annurev-marine-
559 120709-142720
560
561 Shimamura, D., Yamano, T., Niikawa, Y., Hu, D., and Fukuzawa, H. (2023). A pyrenoid-
562 localized protein SAGA1 is necessary for Ca²⁺-binding protein CAS-dependent
563 expression of nuclear genes encoding inorganic carbon transporters in
564 *Chlamydomonas reinhardtii*. *Photosynth. Res.* 156, 181–192. doi: 10.1007/s11120-
565 022-00996-7
566
567 Shimamura, D., Ikeuchi, T., Matsuda, A., Tsuji, Y., Fukuzawa, H., Mochida, K., et al.
568 (2024). Periplasmic carbonic anhydrase CAH1 contributes to high inorganic carbon
569 affinity in *Chlamydomonas reinhardtii*. *Plant Physiol.* 196, 2395–2404. doi:
570 10.1093/plphys/kiac463
571
572 Shimamura, D., Yasuda, J., Yamahara, Y., Nakano, H., Ozawa, S., Tokutsu, R., et al.
573 (2026). A nuclear CobW/WW-domain factor represses the CO₂-concentrating
574 mechanism in the green alga *Chlamydomonas reinhardtii*. *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci.*
575 U.S.A. 123:e2518136123. doi: 10.1073/pnas.2518136123
576
577 Takahashi, Y., Bosmans, K. C., Hsu, P.-K., Paul, K., Seitz, C., Yeh, C.-Y., et al. (2022).
578 Stomatal CO₂/bicarbonate sensor consists of two interacting protein kinases, Raf-like
579 HT1 and non-kinase-activity-requiring MPK12/MPK4. *Sci. Adv.* 8:eabq6161. doi:
580 10.1126/sciadv.abq6161
581
582 Toyokawa, C., Yamano, T., and Fukuzawa, H. (2020). Pyrenoid starch sheath is required
583 for LCIB localization and the CO₂-concentrating mechanism in green algae. *Plant*
584 *Physiol.* 182, 1883–1893. doi: 10.1104/pp.19.01587
585
586 Turkina, M. V., Blanco-Rivero, A., Vainonen, J. P., Vener, A. V., and Villarejo, A.

587 (2006). CO₂ limitation induces specific redox-dependent protein phosphorylation in
588 *Chlamydomonas reinhardtii*. *Proteomics* 6, 2693–2704. doi:
589 10.1002/pmic.200500461
590

591 Wang, Y., and Spalding, M. H. (2014). Acclimation to very low CO₂: contribution of
592 limiting CO₂ inducible proteins, LCIB and LCIA, to inorganic carbon uptake in
593 *Chlamydomonas reinhardtii*. *Plant Physiol.* 166, 2040–2050. doi:
594 10.1104/pp.114.248294
595

596 Wang, L., Yamano, T., Takane, S., Niikawa, Y., Toyokawa, C., Ozawa, S., et al. (2016).
597 Chloroplast-mediated regulation of CO₂-concentrating mechanism by Ca²⁺-binding
598 protein CAS in the green alga *Chlamydomonas reinhardtii*. *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci.*
599 U.S.A. 113, 12586–12591. doi: 10.1073/pnas.1606519113
600

601 Weinel, S., Held, K., Schlücking, K., Steinhorst, L., Kuhlger, S., Hippler, M., et al.
602 (2008). A plastid protein crucial for Ca²⁺-regulated stomatal responses. *New Phytol.*
603 179, 675–686. doi: 10.1111/j.1469-8137.2008.02492.x
604

605 Xiang, Y., Zhang, J., and Weeks, D. P. (2001). The *Cia5* gene controls formation of the
606 carbon concentrating mechanism in *Chlamydomonas reinhardtii*. *Proc. Natl. Acad.*
607 *Sci. U.S.A.* 98, 5341–5346. doi: 10.1073/pnas.101534498
608

609 Xia, L., Alvim, J. C., Nguyen, T.-H., Lefoulon, C., Silva-Alvim, F. A. L., Yu, Z., et al.
610 (2026). A guard cell carbonic anhydrase binds and regulates SLAC1 separate from its
611 catalytic activity. *Nat. Commun.* 17:3911. doi: 10.1038/s41467-026-70596-9
612

613 Yamano, T., Miura, K., and Fukuzawa, H. (2008). Expression analysis of genes
614 associated with the induction of the carbon-concentrating mechanism in
615 *Chlamydomonas reinhardtii*. *Plant Physiol.* 147, 340–354. doi:
616 10.1104/pp.107.114652
617

618 Yamano, T., Tsujikawa, T., Hatano, K., Ozawa, S., Takahashi, Y., and Fukuzawa, H.
619 (2010). Light and low-CO₂-dependent LCIB–LCIC complex localization in the
620 chloroplast supports the carbon-concentrating mechanism in *Chlamydomonas*
621 *reinhardtii*. *Plant Cell Physiol.* 51, 1453–1468. doi: 10.1093/pcp/pcq105
622

- 623 Yamano, T., Fujita, A., and Fukuzawa, H. (2011). Photosynthetic characteristics of a
624 multicellular green alga *Volvox carteri* in response to external CO₂ levels possibly
625 regulated by CCM1/CIA5 ortholog. *Photosynth. Res.* 109, 151–159. doi:
626 10.1007/s11120-010-9614-0
627
- 628 Yamano, T., Sato, E., Iguchi, H., Fukuda, Y., and Fukuzawa, H. (2015). Characterization
629 of cooperative bicarbonate uptake into chloroplast stroma in the green alga
630 *Chlamydomonas reinhardtii*. *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. U.S.A.* 112, 7315–7320. doi:
631 10.1073/pnas.1501659112
632
- 633 Yamano, T., Toyokawa, C., Shimamura, D., Matsuoka, T., and Fukuzawa, H. (2022).
634 CO₂-dependent migration and relocation of LCIB, a pyrenoid-peripheral protein in
635 *Chlamydomonas reinhardtii*. *Plant Physiol.* 188, 1081–1094. doi:
636 10.1093/plphys/kiab528
637
- 638 Yoshioka, S., Taniguchi, F., Miura, K., Inoue, T., Yamano, T., and Fukuzawa, H. (2004).
639 The novel Myb transcription factor LCR1 regulates the CO₂-responsive gene *Cah1*,
640 encoding a periplasmic carbonic anhydrase in *Chlamydomonas reinhardtii*. *Plant Cell*
641 16, 1466–1477. doi: 10.1105/tpc.021162
642

643 **Figure 1. Integrated overview of the *Chlamydomonas* CCM**

644 **(A)** Schematic of a *Chlamydomonas* cell showing the coupling of Ci transport, energy
645 supply, and regulation. Blue arrows indicate Ci/CO₂ flux, magenta arrows indicate
646 energy-related processes, and purple arrows indicate regulatory pathways. The figure
647 integrates CCM modules that are engaged to different extents depending on CO₂
648 availability. Under VLC conditions, HCO₃⁻ is taken up through HLA3, transported
649 across the chloroplast envelope by LCIA, and delivered to the thylakoid lumen through
650 BST1–3, where CAH3 dehydrates HCO₃⁻ to CO₂ near the Rubisco-rich pyrenoid
651 matrix. Under LC conditions, LCII and CAH1 support an alternative CO₂-entry route.
652 LCIB–LCIC localizes around the pyrenoid periphery under VLC conditions and is
653 proposed to recapture CO₂ leaking from the pyrenoid. Energy-related pathways include
654 cyclic electron flow around photosystem I (CEF), flavodiiron protein-dependent
655 pseudo-cyclic electron flow/O₂ photoreduction (PCEF), and chloroplast-to-
656 mitochondrion electron flow (CMEF). CEF and PCEF contribute to thylakoid ΔpH
657 formation, supporting ATP synthesis and luminal CAH3 activity, whereas CMEF and
658 mitochondrial relocation toward the cell periphery may support non-thylakoid Ci uptake
659 steps through respiratory ATP production. KEY1 phosphorylates EPYC1 to regulate
660 pyrenoid condensate dynamics, and CAS mediates chloroplast-to-nucleus signaling that
661 supports CCM gene expression. CCM1/CIA5 controls the induction of many CCM-
662 associated genes under CO₂-limiting conditions. However, except for the LCR1 branch,
663 which regulates CAH1, LCII, and related target genes, whether CCM1/CIA5 directly
664 activates the listed genes or acts through additional transcription factors remains
665 unresolved. Solid arrows indicate established pathways, whereas dashed arrows indicate
666 proposed or incompletely resolved steps. **(B)** Schematic summary of how the regulatory
667 state and chloroplast protein localization of the CCM change under HC, LC, and VLC
668 conditions, as operationally defined in this review. Under HC conditions, CO₂ enters
669 mainly by diffusion, and CBP1 interacts with CCM1/CIA5 to repress a large subset, but
670 not all, of CCM1/CIA5-dependent genes, thereby keeping CCM induction weak. Under
671 LC conditions, CBP1-mediated repression is reduced and CCM1/CIA5-dependent gene
672 induction increases, while LCIB–LCIC remains largely stromal. Under VLC conditions,
673 LCIB–LCIC relocates to the pyrenoid periphery, where it is proposed to contribute to
674 CO₂ leak recapture, and CAS is shown near the pyrenoid to indicate CAS-dependent
675 chloroplast-to-nucleus signaling. Purple arrows indicate CCM1/CIA5-dependent
676 induction rather than proven direct activation of all CCM genes.